

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
CLOCK REPORT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
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Features implemented:

	Multiple light sources		CG specific Algorithms		Hierarchical Menus
	More than 100 primitives		Idle callback		Mouse callback
	Textures		Curves		Keyboard callback
√	Geometric transformation		Menus(1 tier)		Picking
	Camera movement		3-D views		Multiple screens/displays
√	OpenGL functions beyond the VTU syllabus*		Graphic concept beyond the VTU syllabus*		Some form of Intelligence*

INTRODUCTION

OVERVIEW :

The aim of this project is to implement an application package of Computer graphics using OpenGL. Here we represent the concepts displaying Analog clock in OpenGL.

ABOUT GRAPHICS OpenGL:

Activities as wide – ranging as filmmaking, publishing, banking and education continue to undergo revolutionary changes as these technologies alter the ways in which we conduct our daily activities. The combination of computers, network and the complex human visual system, through computer graphics, has led to new ways of displaying information seeing virtual worlds and communicating with people and machines.

A class in computer graphics allows the instructor to build all these topics in a way that can be both informative and fun. Low level algorithms such as those that draw lines or fill polygons are used in OpenGL.

The development of OpenGL resolved both of the difficulties that was experienced with other APIs and with the alternative of using home – brewed s/w . OpenGL today is supported in all platforms.

A clock or watch is called "analog" when it has moving hands and hours marked from 1 to 12 to show you the time.

Analog clocks usually indicate time using angles. The most common [clock face](#) uses a fixed numbered dial or dials and moving hand or hands. It usually has a circular scale of 12 [hours](#), which can also serve as a scale of 60 [minutes](#), and 60 [seconds](#) if the clock has a second hand. Many other styles and designs have been used throughout the years, including dials divided into 6, 8, 10, and 24 hours.

The only other widely used clock face today is the [24 hour analog dial](#) , because of the use of [24 hour time](#) in [military](#) organizations and timetables.

REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

PROJECT REQUIREMENT:

- The background color of the clock is black.
- Each solid cube is representing seconds.
- It contains 3 needles one for hour, one for minute, and one for seconds.
- Large needle represents minute, small needle represent hour and thin needle represents seconds.
- There is a proper delay between needle moments and timings.
- Needle moves from 1 to 12 in clockwise direction.
- It also displays digital clock with date.

The package which we have designed is a one which requires many graphics packages. Most of the functions which are needed to design the package are found in Turbo C compiler with a graphics package. The package requires simple in-built functions found in <GL/glut.h> library. This header file, in addition to the usual header files is needed for the working of the project. For running the program, any basic PC running compatible version of Microsoft Visual Studio is sufficient.

This program should use memory as less as possible, dynamic memory allocation is preferable to accomplish this task. There is no error message produced in this program.

Requirement analysis phase deals with user requirements, which is to fulfill the user's requirement that is known during the problem definition phase. To carry out a requirement analysis, analysts must develop an understanding of the problem domain. The choice of appropriate software for the smooth implementation of the project is accomplished by this.

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT:

The project requires access to the OpenGL graphics library functions . Some of these library functions are contained in unique to C++ library header files such as

- 1) GL/glut.h
- 2) math.h
- 3) windows.h
- 4) time.h

To write, compile and link the program , a suitable C integrated development environment is required . Microsoft Visual Studio/Code Blocks may be suitable in this regard.

Software requirement are:

1. Window Operating System
2. Microsoft Visual Studio
3. Code Blocks

HARDWARE REQUIREMENT:

The minimum/recommended hardware configuration required for developing the proposed software is given below:

- PENTIUM-2 and above compatible systems.
- 128 MB RAM.
- Approximately 1 MB free space in the hard disk.
- Hard disk access time must be less than 19 milliseconds.

DESIGN

Name of the function:

print_screen

Input parameters:

void_print_screen(TYPE xcoord, TYPE ycoord, char *string)

Other functions used:

None

Function description:

This function displays digital clock along with the date.

It includes 2 OpenGL functions glRasterPos3i and glutBitmapCharacter, which renders the character with ASCII code character at the current raster position using the raster font given by font.

The raster position is incremented by the width of the character.

Name of the function:

Draw_clock

Input parameters:

void Draw_clock (TYPE cx, TYPE cy,TYPE cz)

Other functions used:

None

Function description:

This function draws a analog clock.

- Displays clock face by using the OpenGL function gluDisk.
- Displays large wire cube using the OpenGL function gluWireCube.
- Displays hour hand,second hand and minute hand using the OpenGL function gluCylinder.
- Displays solid cube using the OpenGL function gluSolidCube which represents seconds.

Name of the function:

TimeEvent

Input parameter:

void TimeEvent(TYPE variable)

Function description:

This function includes glutTimerFunc it takes 3 Parameters.

- msec- Number of milliseconds to pass before calling the callback.
- Func- The timer callback function.
- value- Integer value to pass to the timer callback.

glutTimerFunc registers the timer callback func to be triggered in at least msec milliseconds. The value parameter to the timer callback will be the value of the value parameter to glutTimerFunc. Multiple timer callbacks at same or differing times may be registered simultaneously.

The number of milliseconds is a lower bound on the time before the callback is generated. GLUT attempts to deliver the timer callback as soon as possible after the expiration of the callback's time interval.

There is no support for canceling a registered callback. Instead, ignore a callback based on its value parameter when it is triggered.

IMPLEMENTATION

```
#include<windows.h>
#include <GL/glut.h>
#include <math.h>
#include <time.h>

void Draw_clock( GLfloat cx, GLfloat cy, GLfloat cz );

time_t ltime;
struct tm *newtime;

GLUquadricObj *Cylinder;
GLUquadricObj *Disk;

GLfloat rx, ry, rz, angle;

// lighting
GLfloat LightAmbient[]= { 2.5, 0.5,1.5,1.0f };
GLfloat LightDiffuse[]= { 0.5, 2.0,1.5, 1.0f };
GLfloat LightPosition[]= { 7.5, 25.0, 15.0, 1.0f };
GLfloat mat_specular[] = { 1.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0 };

void print_screen( int x, int y, char *st)
{
    int l,i;
    l=strlen( st );
    glRasterPos3i( x, y, -1);
    for( i=0; i < l; i++)
    {
        glutBitmapCharacter(GLUT_BITMAP_TIMES_ROMAN_24, st[i]);
    }
}

void display()
{
    time(&ltime);    // Get time
```

```

newtime = localtime(&lttime); // Convert to local time
glClear (GL_COLOR_BUFFER_BIT | GL_DEPTH_BUFFER_BIT);

glMatrixMode (GL_PROJECTION); //Determines the current stack
glLoadIdentity();
glOrtho(-9.0, 9.0, -9.0, 9.0, 1.0, 20.0);
glMatrixMode(GL_MODELVIEW);

glColor3f( 1.0, 1.0, 0.0);
print_screen(-4,-8, asctime(newtime));
Draw_clock( 0.0, 0.0, -14.0);
glutSwapBuffers();
}
static void TimeEvent(int te)
{
    glutPostRedisplay();
    glutTimerFunc( 100, TimeEvent, 1);
}

void init(void)
{
    glClearColor (0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    glShadeModel (GL_SMOOTH);
    glEnable(GL_DEPTH_TEST);

    // Lighting is added to scene
    glLightfv(GL_LIGHT1 ,GL_AMBIENT, LightAmbient);
    glLightfv(GL_LIGHT1 ,GL_DIFFUSE, LightDiffuse);
    glLightfv(GL_LIGHT1 ,GL_POSITION, LightPosition);
    glEnable(GL_LIGHTING);
    glEnable(GL_LIGHT1);

    Cylinder = gluNewQuadric();
    gluQuadricDrawStyle( Cylinder, GLU_FILL);
    gluQuadricNormals( Cylinder, GLU_SMOOTH);
    gluQuadricOrientation( Cylinder, GLU_OUTSIDE);
    gluQuadricTexture( Cylinder, GL_TRUE);

    Disk = gluNewQuadric();
    gluQuadricDrawStyle( Disk, GLU_FILL);
    gluQuadricNormals( Disk, GLU_SMOOTH);
    gluQuadricOrientation( Disk, GLU_OUTSIDE);
    gluQuadricTexture( Disk, GL_TRUE);
}

```

```

}

void Draw_clock( GLfloat cx, GLfloat cy, GLfloat cz )
{

    int hour_ticks , sec_ticks;

    glPushMatrix();
    glTranslatef(cx,cy,cz);
    glRotatef( 180, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0);

    glPushMatrix(); // Draw large wire cube
    glColor3f(1.0, 1.0, 1.0);
    glTranslatef( 0.0, 0.0, 6.0);
    glutWireCube(14.0);
    glPopMatrix();

    glPushMatrix(); // Draw clock face
    glTranslatef( 0, 0, 1.0);
    gluDisk(Disk, 0, 6.35, 72, 6);
    glPopMatrix();

    glPushMatrix(); // Draw hour hand
    glColor3f(1.0, 0.5, 0.5);
    glTranslatef( 0, 0, 0.0);
    glRotatef( (360/12) * newtime->tm_hour + (360/60) * (60 / (newtime->tm_min+1)), 0.0, 0.0, 1.0);
    glPushMatrix();
    glTranslatef(0.0, 0.0, 2.0);

    glPopMatrix();
    glRotatef( 90, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    gluCylinder(Cylinder, 0.75, 0, 4, 16, 16);
    glPopMatrix();

    glPushMatrix(); // Draw minute hand
    glColor3f(1.0, 0.5, 1.0);
    glTranslatef( 0, 0, 0.0);
    glRotatef( (360/60) * newtime->tm_min, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0);
    glPushMatrix();
    glTranslatef(0.0, 0.0, 3.0);
    glScalef(0.5, 0.5, 1.0);
    glPopMatrix();
    glRotatef( 90, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    gluCylinder(Cylinder, 0.5, 0, 6, 16, 16);

```

```

glPopMatrix();

glPushMatrix(); // Draw second hand
glColor3f(1.0, 0.0, 0.5);
glTranslatef( 0, 0, -0.0);
glRotatef( (360/60) * newtime->tm_sec, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0);
glPushMatrix();
glTranslatef(0.0, 0.0, 4.0);
glScalef(0.25, 0.25, 1.0);
glPopMatrix();
glRotatef( 90, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0);
gluCylinder(Cylinder, 0.22, 0, 6, 16, 16);
glPopMatrix();

for(hour_ticks = 0; hour_ticks < 12; hour_ticks++)
{
    glPushMatrix(); // Draw next arm axis.
    glColor3f(0.0, 1.0, 1.0); // give it a color
    glTranslatef(0.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    glRotatef( (360/12) * hour_ticks, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0);
    glTranslatef( 6.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    glPopMatrix();
}

for(sec_ticks = 0; sec_ticks < 60; sec_ticks++)
{
    glPushMatrix();
    glTranslatef(0.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    glRotatef( (360/60) * sec_ticks, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0);
    glTranslatef(6.0, 0.0, 0.0);
    glutSolidCube(0.22);
    glPopMatrix();
}

glPopMatrix();
}

```

```
int main(int argc, char** argv)
{
    glutInit(&argc, argv);
    glutInitDisplayMode (GLUT_DOUBLE | GLUT_RGB);
    glutInitWindowSize (700, 700);
    glutInitWindowPosition (20, 20);
    glutCreateWindow ("CLOCK");
    init ();
    glutDisplayFunc(display);
    glutTimerFunc( 10, TimeEvent, 1);
    glutMainLoop();
    return 0;
}
```

TESING

Testing process of this code is very simple. When we execute the program it displays the current system time properly during both day and night.

It also displays proper digital time along with the date.

USER MANUAL

Original screenshot:

Screenshot without the digital clock:

After changing the background color and clock face:

Without the wire cube and disk:

Without the lighting effect:

CONCLUSION

SUMMARY:

This project shows the graphical representation of a working analogue clock. The objective of this program is to implement simple and basic functions of OpenGL. Computer graphics plays a major role in today's world where visualization takes the upper hand as compared to textual interaction. This is largely true as we can see user interface becoming more and more attractive all thanks to major leaps in the fields of computer graphics. The project is implemented using graphics OpenGL package provided by C.

The above argument is equally justified in the fields of computer simulation which involve complex graphics being highlighted at its peak. It is becoming more and more popular and the constant drive to improve particular system efficiency by studying its simulated model attracts more people towards it.

SCOPE OF IMPROVEMENT :

Though the package that is designed here does not include complex OpenGL package, we intend to improve this by including extra features like lighting effects, Changing the background color adding alarms. We do this with an aim to attract more people to use our package

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